

STORYTELLING-BASED ACTIVITIES AND THE SPEAKING PROFICIENCY OF GRADE 7 STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Speaking is one of the vital skills that should be acquired by the students in English classroom. Utilization of effective teaching techniques are essential in teaching speaking for the students to enhance their oral skills. Relative to this, the study aimed to determine the effects of storytelling-based activities on the speaking proficiency of Grade 7 students of Sampaguita Village National High School, A.Y. 2020-2021. This study is experimental in nature as it investigated the effects of a teaching technique i.e. storytelling-based activity with great emphasis on the respondents' speaking proficiency. It is aspired to find out the significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores of the respondents in their speaking proficiency before and after using story-telling activities. Thirty (30) respondents of grade 7 students from Sampaguita Village National High School were used and the study covered in two weeks. The researcher used a teacher-made pre and post assessment speaking activity, exemplars and a speaking assessment rubric as the instruments of the study. Statistical treatment utilized in the study was mean, standard deviation, frequency, percentages, and sample t-test. The result showed that there was a significant difference between the pretest and posttest of the respondents in their speaking proficiency before and after using story-telling activities. This implies that the use of storytelling-based activities has great contribution in enhancing the speaking skills of the students. Thus, rejecting the null hypothesis. Since the use of storytelling-based activities improved the speaking skills of the students, teachers and administrators can use storytelling-based activities as a technique in teaching speaking. Additionally, extension center for speaking can be organized to promote speaking in English and for students to practice or enhance their skills in speaking.

Keywords: storytelling activities, speaking, grammar, vocabulary, pronunciation, comprehension, fluency